

Phonemic Awareness and Phonics Instruction and their Impacts on Reading Outcomes in Early Reading Development

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Abstract

This research investigates phonemic awareness and phonics instruction and their impacts on reading outcomes in early reading development in Ali-Sabieh. Using a quasi-experimental research design, the study tests the proposed intervention on a control and experiment group of Kindergarteners in Ali-Sabieh. The data collected enabled post-test scores to determine the effect of participating in phonics and/or phonemic awareness instruction in isolation and compare these average score gains with similar students not participating in any supplementary instruction (according to students with similar pre-test scores and similar baseline test scores). Data were collected from 3 schools and a total of 120 students, 40 from each school. The teachers played the role of administering the tests and implementing the proposed intervention. The results suggest that through phonemic awareness and phonics instructions interventions, reading outcomes can significantly be improved in children whose first language is not English in Ali-Sabieh, Djibouti. This instructional strategy also showed the potential of guaranteeing early reading development success.

Keywords: phonics instructions, reading outcomes, early reading development

Introduction

In 2000, the National Reading Panel (NRP) established five components of effective literacy instruction: phonic, phonemic awareness, comprehension, fluency and vocabulary (Pressley & Fingeret, 2007; Murray, 2016; Dziedzic, 2022) and concluded that phonics instructions and phonemic awareness ought to be increased in primary grades. Heggerty, Hollmann and VanHekken (2020) defined phonemic awareness (PA) as the understanding that spoken words are made up of individual sounds identified as *phonemes*. Hodgins and Harrison (2021) also mentioned that phonemic awareness is auditory and oral and that the focus is particularly on the sounds in the words. While phonemic awareness is solely auditory and oral, phonics instruction is both auditory and visual (Andorka, 2021; Feldman, 2021) and focuses on letter-sound relationship. Here, children are taught the letter or the letter combinations that form the phonemes or sounds in the language.

Research has consistently shown that literacy skills are linked to several benefits that are both long-lasting and substantial (French, Gagné & Collins, 2020; Zijlstra et al., 2021). Birch and Fulop (2020), for instance, highlighted the importance of developing phonics-related skills in L2 language reading whereby L2 referred to the learning of the English language as both a foreign or a second language. The researchers also lamented on how these skills have been accorded less attention in an L2 reading classroom as a result of the over-emphasis on the complete language principles of reading instruction. A meta-analysis by Murphy Odo (2021) on the effectiveness of phonemic awareness and/or phonics instructions on pseudo word and word reading on English as an L2 showed that phonemic awareness and phonics instructions had a moderate impact on L2 reading. Similarly, Olinger's (2023) results showed that supplemental phonemic awareness lessons on phonological instruction and spelling development positively affected spelling development and phonemic awareness and phonic instructions.

French is the primary language of instruction in Djibouti (USIAD, 2021) and with that arises a conspicuous absence of research that focuses on the effects of phonemic awareness and phonics instruction -typically implemented in the English Language- on early reading development. This is particularly concerning since phonics instructions exercises in the English language are likely to influence literacy outcomes in an educational setting dominated by the French language (Garrido-Pozú, 2024). Additionally, the lack of Ali-Sabieh-specific studies on the topic impedes the understanding of how phonemic awareness and phonics instruction interventions influence reading proficiency among children which could potentially lead to suboptimal educational strategies in Ali-Sabieh.

The significance of this study lies in its potential to improve early reading interventions by ensuring teachers, professionals in the field and the government understands how phonemic awareness and phonic instructions in English language as an L2, affect literacy in a French-dominated setting. This could potentially inform the tailoring of educational practices and ultimately, enhance reading outcomes in Ali-Sabieh.

The following questions are investigated:

Is it possible to improve reading outcomes through phonemic awareness and phonics instructions interventions in children whose first language is not English? And if so, does this guarantee early reading development success?

Literature Review

Phonemic Awareness

Phonemic awareness is the understanding of the smallest units of sound in words, the phonemes, and the ability to manipulate them. This skill is essential in the process of learning to read because it enables the child to understand that words are made up of phonemes that can be separated, combined, and manipulated. This is why its significance is stressed as it can predict future reading success rather adequately. Buckingham et al. (2023) stated that phonemic awareness was a better predictor of reading comprehension than IQ and SES. Other studies argued that it is only useful in the initial levels of reading only while others view it as useful at any level of reading. For instance, Ehri et al. (2001) found out that students with good phonemic awareness can decode new words

and are likely to be good readers with good comprehension. On the other hand, children who do not have such skills encounter difficulties in reading and even understanding what they read. However, phonemic awareness should be taught as one of the components of literacy, and not in isolation as it has been (Hauck, 2021).

Instructional Methods

Effective instructional activities for teaching phonemic awareness are characterized by a multitude of interactive, engaging activities focusing on sound manipulation both auditorily and orally (Irvine-Apps, 2002). Important strategies include segmenting, blending, and manipulation of phonemes within words. Segmenting is the process of breaking words apart into individual phonemes so that children can hear the individual sounds that make up words (Hall-Kenyon & Culatta, 2012). For example, the word "cat" can be segmented into the phonemes /k/, /æ/, and /t/ (Wicklund, 2004). An essential strategy, blending, is the ability of children to take individual phonemes and blend them into a word. Blending phonemes is an important skill for children to develop when they encounter an unfamiliar word in text, it is through blending that they can decode the word. Sometimes, you might present a child with sound sequences like /s/, /i/, /t/, and the child will blend these sounds to say "sit". A further example of developing phonemic awareness includes the ability to manipulate phonemes, such that phonemes are manipulated within words, by addition, deletion, or substitution to develop phonemic awareness. For example, the /h/ in "hat" changed to /b/ results in "bat". Studies show that children's inclusion of such activities in daily literacy instruction significantly improves their phonemic awareness (Ehri et al., 2001). In one recent study conducted by Al Otaiba et al. (2019), it was found that when phonemic awareness is explicitly and systematically taught, reading and spelling significantly increase. This impact is also significant when instruction in phonemic awareness is integrated with phonics instruction. Lastly, the use of engaging activities that are game-like keeps children motivated while learning phonemic awareness and is both fun and effective.

Phonics Instruction

Phonics, one of the most effective instructional approaches in early literacy teaching, is deliberately planned to develop the relationship between phonemes and graphemes, which enhances children's reading and spelling abilities (Schatz, 2020). This pedagogical approach prepares the learners for proficient reading by ensuring that they acquire all the skills that enable them to read written language properly. Rohde (2015) stated that it has a very important function in early literacy. Research by Ashby et al. (2013) posited that systematic phonics instruction is highly effective in enhancing reading and spelling skills. As phonics teaching and learning engages the learners in the systematic study of the relationship between letters and sounds, it enables the learners to read with precision and confidence (Boe, 2023). In this way, children learn to decode words on their own, thus strengthening their reading skills and the ability to comprehend what they read. Therefore, phonics instruction remains one of the most effective strategies for promoting the literacy skills that are crucial for learning and academic achievement.

The effectiveness of phonics instruction significantly depends on its structured and explicit implementation. Synthetic phonics, in which children learn to convert letters into sounds and blend them to form words, has been widely acknowledged for its effectiveness in early reading education (Eshiet, 2014). Although phonics instruction provides clear benefits, it should be complemented

with other reading strategies, such as vocabulary and comprehension instruction, to design a comprehensive literacy program (Gambrell et al., 2011). Therefore, while phonics is an important stepping stone for the process of decoding, an overall literacy approach that includes plural teaching methods helps in overall reading ability. Embedding phonics as part of the overall literacy program ensures that children acquire not only the skills to decode words but also the skills for comprehension and critical thinking, thus laying a solid foundation for literacy success throughout life.

Combining Phonemic Awareness and Phonics Instruction

The integration of a phonemic awareness and phonics approach in educational curricula is a vital component for the development of overall reading skills. Phonemic awareness, defined as the understanding of how to work with all of the sounds in words, and phonics instruction, defined as the process of associating sounds with the letters or letter combinations that represent them, both contribute to the development of foundational literacy skills (Moore, 2021). Research by studies such as Moore (2021) supports the need to combine these two instructional components. A balanced approach will produce students who can both isolate and manipulate individual phonemes as well as understand how sounds correspond to the alphabetic system. The integration of these two helps children perceive not only the segmentation and blending of sounds but also the way sound-letter relationships help to represent spoken words (Webber et al., 2024). However, effective integration requires careful planning and implementation. However, integration needs to be properly organized and followed through. Teachers need to design curricula that provide explicit instruction within both phonemic awareness and phonics and include a range of interactive activities to help consolidate and integrate these skills (Fossum, 2013). Integration of both phonemic awareness and phonics instruction within educational programs creates a strong foundation for early reading. When both aspects are combined, a teacher will be able to prepare students well with the competencies that are necessary for reading.

Implementation Strategies

To maximize the effectiveness of the integration of phonemic awareness and phonics, instruction in all educational curricula must be approached strategically. One approach is scaffolded instruction beginning with explicit phonemic activities and then slowly integrating phonics (Wicklund, 2004). By following this sequence, children first learn to become phonemically aware and then are explicitly taught to become phonics readers, which sets the student up with a sound understanding of reading and reading development. Scaffolding must also prioritize teacher training. Teachers need to be trained on how to teach both investigative and phonics lessons with precision (Stainthorp, 2020). This involves having adequate knowledge of the scientific foundation of the instruction, as well as access to the resources and guidance to support students accordingly. Furthermore, teachers have to select carefully the content and tasks that will be used in the classroom to support the curricular objectives and meet the needs of the learners. The Jolly Phonics is a good example of a program that has all these features besides offering complete materials and lesson plans on how to integrate phonemic awareness and phonics instruction (Carpenter, 2021). These often include a mix of activities tailored to reach a range of learning styles and abilities. Assessment and Progress Monitoring are crucial for forecasting and modifying the nature of instruction as required (Torgesen et al., 2017). Ongoing assessment is important to identify students who are potentially falling behind in learning. The information collected periodically from

the assessments may be used to ensure all students receive the required level of support to make progress in accomplishing effective reading skills.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted a quasi-experimental design; this design is typically used in studies that investigate the causal relationship between a dependent and an independent variable, but the researcher is unable to randomly assign participants to various groups (Thyer, 2012; Campbell & Stanley, 2015; Janssen & Kollar, 2021). The current research is educational, this means that students are already classified into specific groups or classes based on several factors such as their grade, schools or even existing classroom structures. Therefore, the random assignment of students to other different groups would have likely disrupted normal classroom environment and the learning process. By adopting a quasi-experimental design, the researcher was able to work with the naturally occurring groups, ensuring the study was less disruptive and more feasible.

Researchers such as Steinberg and Sartain (2015) and Glewwe et al. (2021) suggested that the implementation of a true experimental design with random assignment requires substantial coordination and resources, potentially across multiple classrooms and schools. Contrastingly, a quasi-experimental design allowed for a more manageable structure by utilizing existing groups and working within the various limitations of available resources in the schools. This is of particular importance in areas with limited educational infrastructure such as Djibouti, as highlighted by Salhi and Sihem (2018) and Seife (2020).

Participants and Study Setting

Recruitment

Education in Djibouti begins in kindergarten or preschool after which the children advance to primary school. Children begin pre-school at the age of 3 and graduate to primary school by the age of 5, however, according to an article by StudyCountry (n, d), only a small percentage of the children enrol in this level because of financial constraints. As a result, the study focused on children in the first grade of primary school (*École Primaire*), who, typically, are aged 6 or younger. While taking into account the student-teacher ratio, recruitment criteria and resource availability, the study recruited 120 children, from three primary schools in Ali-Sabieh.

Upon recruitment, children were exposed to a pre-intervention test that followed the AIMSweb Test of Early Literacy (TEL). The test included a *phoneme segmentation* test labelled Appendix A where children were required to identify the phonemes in the words read by the teacher and read them aloud with each correct identification earning each child a point. This is illustrated in Appendix A. The second test, identified as the *letter-word-sound* test involved the child pronouncing the letter sounds on the first five columns of boxes and making the consonant sound on the next five columns of boxes with each correct pronunciation in each column earning a child three points. For instance, a child was expected to begin with the consonant sound (/d/), then the VC (/og/), then the CVC (/dog/). This is illustrated in Appendix B. Based on the scores of the pre-test intervention, the teachers then assigned the children into two groups; the experiment group (Phonics Instructions + Phonemic Awareness) and the control group.

Recruitment Criteria

The children were recruited based on the following criteria:

- i. Children are in the first grade of Primary School.
- ii. Children are non-native English speakers with limited proficiency in the English language.
- iii. Children whose parents have given consent.

Setting

The setting of the study was in the classrooms of the three schools; this was aimed at ensuring that a natural learning environment was maintained and disruptions minimized. The researcher designed the interventions in a manner that they could be integrated seamlessly into the daily school schedule to ensure continuity and consistency in learning. The distribution of the children saw the three schools host 20 children for the experimental group and 20 others for the control group. The distribution provided a robust dataset for the analysis and most importantly, ensured a balanced comparison across the different learning environments.

Instrument and Intervention

Phonemic Awareness Intervention

The researcher designed this intervention to improve the ability of the children to identify and produce individual sounds in spoken words; a skill considered essential in spelling and reading development (Adams et al. 1998). Two activities were included in this intervention: phoneme segmentation activity and phoneme blending activity. The two activities took place in three weeks, two sessions per week and each child was allocated 10 minutes per session. Teachers were also briefed on the activities and how to assess the children.

The *phoneme segmentation activity* involved giving a child a piece of paper with either three or four boxes drawn on it; the boxes had the sounds of the word being pronounced. The teacher would then be required to say a word out loud, for instance, ‘dog’ and its sound (/d/ - /o/ - /g/) and ask the child to repeat the word and pronounce each sound slowly. The child was then required to point each sound using a pencil or a finger that corresponded to what they heard from the teacher. The teacher then repeated the activity with different words, each time increasing the difficulty to identify and pronounce the sound. As illustrated in Appendix C, the activity was adopted and modified from a curriculum designed by Adam et al. (1998).

The *phoneme blending activity* involved teachers creating flashcards and giving them to the children. Each flashcard had a single phoneme of the word pronounced by the teacher, for instance, for the word ‘cat,’ the child received three flashcards for each phoneme (/k/ - /a/ - /t/). The child was then required to pronounce each phoneme while identifying the flashcards, after which, the teacher was required to encourage the child into putting together the phonemes to create a word and say the sound and word out loud. This is illustrated in Appendix D. The activity was modified from Honig et al.’s (2018) Teaching Reading Sourcebook.

Phonics Instructions Intervention

The researcher designed this intervention to educate children on the existing relationship between sounds and letters. The intervention involved one activity that focused on the letter-sound relationship that was expected to improve English comprehension and fluency; the activity was identified as the letter-sound correspondence activity. The activity also took place in three weeks, two sessions per week and each child allocated 10 minutes per session. Teachers were also briefed on the activities and how to assess the children.

The *letter-sound correspondence activity* involved teachers creating flashcards of the letter of the alphabets and picture cards of the items the alphabets represented and issuing it to a child. The teacher was required to pick a picture card and show it to the child while identifying the object on the picture, for instance, 'ball.' The child was then required to identify and say out loud the first letter of the picture, for instance /b/ for 'ball' and identify the correspondent flashcard with the letter of the alphabet, after which, the child would place the picture card next to the flashcard. This activity was repeated to reinforce the letter-sound relationship. This is illustrated in Appendix E with the researcher modifying the activity from McGuinness' (2004) Book.

Data Collection

Pre-test and post-intervention measures

Pre- and post-intervention tests (Appendix A and B) followed the AIMSweb Test of Early Literacy (TEL) to identify the baseline measure of the current literacy skills before the intervention and measure the literacy skills and establish the effectiveness of the activities after the intervention. A pre-intervention test was administered four days to 120 students collectively before the intervention and a similar post-intervention test administered to the two groups (control and experiment groups) four days after the intervention.

Reliability and Validity

The reliability of the interventions was guaranteed by ensuring that the assessments were administered consistently across all children and teachers. Additionally, the aspect of inter-reliability was maintained through the two training sessions representing each intervention, specifically for teachers. The aspect of validity was ensured by using validated activities that had been assessed by the teachers and the researcher's supervisor to ensure that the activities aligned with the objective of the study.

The AIMSweb PS measure also demonstrated reliability and validity through a previous study that had been carried out by Elliot et al.'s (2001) kindergarten settings. The reliability of the phonemic segmentation assessment was established by several other standardized assessments such as Reading Skills and Woodcock-Johnson Reading with a score of $r = .60$ and $r = .44$, respectively. The validity of the assessment had been demonstrated by Pre-Reading Total Scores ($r = .54$) and Developing Skills Checklist, among others.

Elliot et al. (2001) also assessed the validity and reliability of tests that focused on phonics instructions in the AIMSweb. The researchers discovered that the retest reliability recorded .90.

Validity was established with the Woodcock-Johnson Broad ($r = .63$) and Reading Skills ($r = .75$), among others.

Data Analysis

The study adopted descriptive statistics to calculate the standard deviations, means and frequency deviations of both the pre- and post-intervention scores from the control and experimental groups. Inferential statistics, including t-tests, compared the post-intervention scores between the groups while controlling for pre-intervention scores.

Ethical Considerations

Regarding ethical considerations, the researcher obtained informed consent from the guardians or the parents of the children guaranteeing them that the confidentiality of the data from the participants will be maintained. Additionally, teachers and parents were informed that the researcher had taken measures to minimize any form of discomfort or distress during the activities and assessment, and that participants had a right to withdraw from the intervention at the time they felt uncomfortable. The research received ethical clearance and oversight from Jiangsu University.

Results

After taking the scores of all the 120 participating learners, the teachers divided the learners into the control and experiment groups using random sampling, to ensure that the cognitive abilities of learners from both groups is roughly balanced out. This is to ensure that differences in cognitive abilities do not affect the final results.

Table 4.1 and 4.2 show the results of the test scores from Table 1 and Table 2 (appendix) for the control and experiment group, after the intervention. As shown in Table 4.1, the mean score for the control group was 31.84% while the mean score for the experiment group was 77.35%, indicating that learners in the experiment group performed better.

Table 4.1

Paired Samples Statistics					
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Test scores Control (%)	31.83616	60	2.613784	.340286
	Test scores Experiment(%)	77.34746		7.739873	1.007646
			60		

Table 4.2 investigates whether or not these differences in performance were statistically significant. In Table 4.2, $t_{58} = -49.071$, p value < 0.05 , indicating that the experiment group's

performance was better and statistically significantly different from the control group's performance.

Table 4.2

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Test scores Control (%) - Test scores Experiment(%)	-45.5113	7.123947	0.927459	-47.36781	-43.65479	-49.071	58	0.000

The intervention also involved administering a questionnaire, where teachers evaluated the young learners from both control (section 4) and experimental (section 5) groups in terms of how well they could segment words into individual sounds, blend individual sounds to create words, recognise and produce sounds for different letters of the alphabet, self-correct errors while reading or identifying sounds, and adjust the pace of reading, blending or correspondence when complex words are introduced.

Table 4.3 also shows that the mean average score on the questionnaire for the control group was 1.325 and for the experiment group was 4.706, on a Likert scale where 1-poor and 5-excellent. From these statistics, the experiment group also outperformed the control group.

Table 4.3

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Error
Pair 1	Control Group average Score (questionnaire)	1.325	60	.3738	.0483	
	Experiment Group average Score (questionnaire)	4.706	60	.3862	.0499	

Table 4.4 seeks to determine if this difference is significant. In Table 4.4, $t_{59} = -43.041$, p value < 0.05 , indicating that the experiment group's performance was better and statistically significantly different from the control group's performance.

Table 4.4

		Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Control Group average Score (questionnaire) - Experiment Group average Score (questionnaire)	- 3.3806	0.6084	0.0785	- 3.5377	- 3.2234	- 43.041	59	0.000

Discussion

The findings of the study indicated that reading outcomes among young learners, whose first language is not English, can be improved through phonemic awareness and phonics instructions interventions. This is consistent with most of the literature cited in this study, including (Stainthorp, 2020; Moore, 2021; Hauck, 2021). The main theoretical implications of the study were that the findings provided more evidence from an African country that the proposed instructional strategy is robust in justifying rapid early reading development. More evidence was provided that Djiboutian children, in accordance with the proposed intervention, acquired phonemic awareness before learning letter sound knowledge when they made a transition from spoken to written language. The study found that phonemic awareness and phonics instruction had significant positive effects on the reading outcomes. These findings provide important insights for parents, educators, students, and people preparing to become educators and researchers interested in early reading development.

An effective intervention for struggling readers with reading difficulties relies significantly on systematic instruction in phonemic awareness and phonics. Many studies reveal that these two practices are critical to the efficacy of children with difficulty reading. According to research, it is evident through the collected data that teaching students with explicit instructions on issues of

phonemic awareness and phonics greatly improves their decoding skills and reading fluency (Suggate, 2016). Students who have difficulties reading may be greatly supported with interventions that focus on phonemic awareness along with systematic phonics instruction, specifically using the Orton-Gillingham approach, this extends to students with dyslexia (Sayeski et al., 2019). Students who are experiencing inconsistency in their progress in learning how to read should also receive interventions in other areas of vocabulary knowledge, comprehension strategies, and reading fluency to enhance their reading. In addition, interventions need to be individualized and implemented with high fidelity to maximize success. Therefore, in helping struggling readers, even though it has been established that phonemic awareness and phonics instruction form a foundation, other areas need to be factored in an overall instructional perspective with various layers of support.

Phonemic awareness and phonics are vital for all students, but for English Language Learners, they come with some specific linguistic and cultural variables. Research has shown that ELLs need intensive, explicit instruction in phonemic awareness and phonics because of the complexities stemming from English phonetics and phonetic orthography (Zoski, 2015). While the content could readily support top-down instruction, for translation to be effective, delivery might also need to consider ELLs' multilingual backgrounds and language experiences. For instance, various studies have shown that phonemic awareness tasks can and should embed phonological features of their native languages' speech sounds to capitalize effectively on skill transfer (Alshammari, 2015; Coulter-Glazier, 2022). Task relevance of task and engagement is significantly improved when using culturally relevant materials and examples. However, the key challenges such as ELLs' limited proficiency in English and their different educational backgrounds call for responsive learning contexts to ensure the provision of tailored instruction and extra support. In light of this, while phonemic awareness and phonics instructions are beneficial for the development of literacy among ELLs, a culturally responsive and flexible approach is necessary to meet their needs and bring out optimal results.

Conclusion

The results suggest that through phonemic awareness and phonics instructions interventions, reading outcomes can significantly be improved in children whose first language is not English in Ali-Sabieh, Djibouti. This instructional strategy also showed the potential of guaranteeing early reading development success. One of the most revealing findings in this study is the positive impact of word recognition skills on reading comprehension skills. Additionally, the fact that oral language skills such as semantic fluency and semantic access have been found to drive word recognition was consistent with results found within previous research. These results show the related tasks of lexical decision and word naming are highly related to early reading development in Djibouti. Taken together, the results of the current study have the potential to inform best-practice literacy practices. This information has potential benefit for government and educational stakeholders and could potentially improve both national and international early reading instruction. Finally, future research implications include the need for repetitions with larger samples and in-depth case studies to explore contextual factors that may play a part in the relationship between phonemic awareness and phonics instruction and better reading outcomes.

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Appendix

Appendix A. Phoneme segmentation test

Figure 1. The following is a figure of the phoneme segmentation test page issued to 120 students, collectively, pre-intervention and to both the control and experiment groups post-intervention.

Source: AimsWebPlus (2021)

Table 1. Phoneme Segmentation Test Scores

Student Number.....

Word	Score
Cap - /k/ - /a/ - /p/	
Log - /l/ - /o/ - /g/	

Hug - /h/ - /u/ - /g/	
Mess - /m/ - /e/ - /s/	
Shock - /sh/ - /o/ - /k/	
	Total Score:

Appendix B. Letter-word-sound test

Figure 2. The following is a figure of the letter-word-sound test page issued to 120 students, collectively, pre-intervention and to both the control and experiment groups post-intervention

Source: *AimsWebPlus* (2021)

Table 2. Letter-word-sound tests scores

Student Number.....

/m/	/t/	/z/	/m/	/d/
/s/	/b/	/f/	/v/	/p/
/p/	/h/	/n/	k/	w/
Score:	Score:	Score:	Score:	Score:

d	c	b	w	T
og	a	us	ig	en
dog	cap	bus	wig	ten
Score:	Score:	Score:	Score:	Score:

Appendix C

Phoneme Segmentation Activity

No. of weeks	No. of sessions	Activity	General Instructions
Week 1	Session 1	Dog - /d/ - /o/ - /g/	Give a child a piece of paper with either three or four boxes drawn on each box representing the sounds of the words being pronounced. As the teacher, say the word and its sounds out loud and ask the child to repeat the word and pronounce each sound. While pronouncing, ask the child to point the sound. The teacher repeats this activity with different words each time increasing difficulty.
		Cat - /k/ - /a/ - /t/	
	Session 2	Sun - /s/ - /u/ - /n/	
		Hat - /h/ - /a/ - /t/	
		Pig - /p/ - /i/ - /g/	
Week 2	Session 1	Hand - /h/ - /a/ - /n/ - /d/	
		Stop - /s/ - /t/ - /o/ - /p/	
	Session 2	Fast - /f/ - /a/ - /s/ - /t/	

		Milk - /m/ - /i/ - /l/ - /k/	
Week 3	Session 1	Flag- /f/ /l/ /æ/ /g/	
		Stop - /s/ /t/ /v/ /p/	
	Session 2	Lamp - /l/ /æ/ /m/ /p/	
		Jump - /j/ - /u/ - /m/ - /p/	

Figure 3. Phoneme Segmentation Activity for the experiment group

Appendix D**Phoneme Blending Activity**

No. of weeks	No. of sessions	Activity	General Instructions
Week 1	Session 1	On - /o/ - /n/	Give a child flashcards, each with a single phoneme of the words you pronounce. Ask the child to pronounce each phoneme while identifying it on the flashcards given. Encourage the child to put together the phonemes to create the word you mentioned and say it out loud.
		At - /a/ - /t/	
	Session 2	Up - /u/ - /p/	
		If - /i/ - /f/	
Week 2	Session 1	Fan - /f/ - /a/ - /n/	
		Sun - /s/ - /u/ - /n/	
	Session 2	Dog - /d/ - /o/ - /g/	
		Cat - /k/ - /a/ - /t/	
Week 3	Session 1	Fish - /f/ /i/ /sh/	
		Slip - /s/ /l/ /i/ /p/	
	Session 2	Lamp - /l/ /æ/ /m/ /p/	

		Jump - /j/ - /u/ - /m/ - /p/	
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Figure 4. Phoneme Blending Activity for the experiment group

Appendix E**Letter-sound Correspondence Activity**

No. of weeks	No. of sessions	Activity	General Instructions
Week 1	Session 1	a, b, c, d	Issue flashcards of the letters of the alphabet and picture cards of the items the letter represents to the child. Pick a picture card and show the child while identifying the object on the picture. Ask the child identify and say out loud the first letter of the picture and pick the corresponding flashcard with the letter mentioned. Ask the child to place the picture card next to the flashcard. Repeat this activity.
	Session 2	e, f, g, h	
Week 2	Session 1	i, j, k, l	
	Session 2	m, n, o, p	
Week 3	Session 1	q, r, s, t, u	
	Session 2	v, w, x, y, z	

Figure 5. Letter-sound correspondence activity for the experiment group.**Appendix F****Questionnaire****Section 1. General Information**

School Number (either 1, 2 or 3).....

Student Number.....

Teacher Initials.....

Section 2. Phoneme Segmentation Test

The following image is a phoneme segmentation test -modified from the AIMSweb Test of Early Literacy (TEL)- issued to 120 students in the three schools, pre-intervention. In each school, teachers are requested to fill in the scores of the 40 students and send the results to the following e-mail address: jfk808813@gmail.com.

Teachers are also requested to issue the same test, post-intervention, to the control and experiment groups in each school, fill the scores and send them to the following e-mail address: jfk808813@gmail.com. The e-mail address belongs to the researcher.

cap	/k/ /a/ /p/
log	/l/ /o/ /g/
shock	/sh/ /o/ /k/
mess	/m/ /e/ /s/
hug	/h/ /u/ /g/

Word	Score
Cap - /k/ - /a/ - /p/	
Log - /l/ - /o/ - /g/	
Hug - /h/ - /u/ - /g/	
Mess - /m/ - /e/ - /s/	
Shock - /sh/ - /o/ - /k/	
	Total Score:

Section 3. Letter-word-sound Test

The following is a letter-word-sound test modified from the AIMSweb Test of Early Literacy (TEL) issued to 120 students in the three schools. In each school, teachers are requested to fill in the scores of the 40 students and send the results to the following e-mail address: jfk808813@gmail.com.

Teachers are also requested to issue the same test, post-intervention, to the control and experiment groups in each school, fill in the scores and send them to the following e-mail address: *jfk808813@gmail.com*. The e-mail address belongs to the researcher.

m	f	z	m	d
s	b	f	v	p
p	h	n	k	w

d	c	b	w	t
og	ap	us	ig	en
dog	cap	bus	wig	ten

/m/	/t/	/z/	/m/	/d/
/s/	/b/	/f/	/v/	/p/
/p/	/h/	/n/	k/	w/
Score:	Score:	Score:	Score:	Score:
d	c	b	w	T
og	a	us	ig	en
dog	cap	bus	wig	ten
Score:	Score:	Score:	Score:	Score:

Section 4

The section focuses on teachers that dealt with the control group. Please respond to each statement by clicking on your response indicating the extent of your disagreement or agreement. Tick your responses as: Strongly disagree (1), Disagree (2), Neutral (3), Agree (4), Strongly agree (5).

Assessment	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Student can segment words into individual sounds					
Student can blend individual sounds to create words.					

Student can read fluently					
Student can recognise and produce sounds for different letters of the alphabet.					
Student can self-correct errors while reading or identifying sounds.					
Student is able to adjust the pace of reading, blending or correspondence when complex words are introduced.					

Section

5

The section focuses on teachers that dealt with the experiment group. Please respond to each statement by clicking on your response indicating the extent of your disagreement or agreement. Tick your responses as: Strongly disagree (1), Disagree (2), Neutral (3), Agree (4), Strongly agree (5).

Assessment	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Student can segment words into individual sounds					
Student can blend individual sounds to create words.					
Student can read fluently					
Student can recognise and produce sounds for different letters of the alphabet.					

Student can self-correct errors while reading or identifying sounds.					
Student is able to adjust the pace of reading, blending or correspondence when complex words are introduced.					